

Table 2, including a comparison with results of the Votex thresher operating under similar conditions. The parameters were chosen to be realistic assessments in the Senegalese context, based on earlier trials and current work. With a 12-hp diesel motor and 6 workers, the ASI yields 6,000 kg d⁻¹ of clean rice from manually harvested production in fields with yields of approximately 4.5 t ha⁻¹. Under similar operating conditions, the Votex capacity is 4,300 kg d⁻¹. The separation recovery rate was 99% in on-farm tests for the ASI, much higher than the Votex's 85%. Thus, with the ASI, total labor needed is 6 workers. No additional labor is needed for sifting the straw for unthreshed rice or for winnowing, because of the efficient separation of rice from straw. Daily perform-

ance for both machines depends on the relative grain to straw proportion, the grain yield, the moisture content of the straw, and the speed of input of harvested crop.

The financial analysis evaluates the profitability of the machine for a service operator in order to assess potential distribution. With a purchase price of US\$4,138 and the parameters in Table 2, the cost per ton for the ASI is US\$9.23, when operator labor is the only labor included (the current system). For the Votex, per-ton costs are only slightly higher (\$9.32). The ASI's net revenues are more than double the revenues for the Votex, primarily because of the higher processing rate. ASI's benefit-cost ratio of 1.7 is in the acceptable range for investments, even with only 55 workdays yr⁻¹.

In addition to revenues for the ASI owner, farmers also benefit. The ASI has a high quality of output and reduces the time for postharvest work. This in turn lowers postharvest grain losses that arise from delays and loss of humidity. Labor for winnowing, cleaning, and sifting, which is usually supplied by the farm household, is no longer needed. The modified ASI helps reduce calendar constraints to double cropping, avoid grain losses from delays, reduce total harvest and post-harvest costs, and provide local employment in artisan workshops and agroindustry. In terms of demand, SISMAR, the local manufacturer of the ASI, is unable to meet current demand for the machine. ■

Technology transfer from Asia to Africa sets the stage for public- and private-sector collaboration in new technology in Senegal

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In the early 1990s, the productivity and profitability of irrigated systems in the Senegal River Valley began to be questioned. The Senegal River Valley Development Authority (known as SAED) found that harvest and postharvest constraints were very important, both in costs and in grain quality losses. SAED agents therefore turned to research, specifically to the Senegalese Agricultural Research Institute (known by the French acronym ISRA) and to WARDA to help find alternatives.

In response to WARDA's request, IRRI donated prototypes of the TC800 axial flow thresher/cleaner and the SG800 stripper gatherer. WARDA and ISRA modified the TC800, with help from SAED, a local artisan, farmers, and local agro-industry. By November 1997, a new thresher/cleaner, known as the ASI, was released in Senegal. A

companion article by Wopereis et al, page 39, presents the technical and financial results. Here, we present the development process of the ASI, an example of how research, development, private industry, and farmers can work together to meet technology needs.

IRRI researchers developed the SG800 and the TC800 to meet the needs of small-scale Asian rice farmers. Early in 1995, with the IRRI-donated prototypes and construction plans, IRRI and WARDA collaborated with SAED and ISRA to assess the potential of the machines in Sahelian irrigated rice production systems. In November 1995, during the wet-season harvest, an IRRI agricultural engineer (B. Douthwaite) assisted technicians and machinists with field tests of the machines. These people developed a list of changes recommended to strengthen the machine and adapt it, particularly for use with manually harvested fields and under wet field conditions. A workshop was organized with the major stakeholders involved, including farmers, rice millers, local manufacturers, representatives from the development agencies (SAED, etc.), researchers from WARDA and ISRA,

and extension agents, to discuss test results and future work.

WARDA, SAED, and ISRA decided to work with a local artisan skilled with agricultural machinery in order to build a Senegalese prototype, using the existing TC800 model and the IRRI plans. One of the challenges was to build the machines with locally available materials. The artisan chosen was skilled with agricultural machinery (including the existing Votex thresher), and his machine shop was sufficiently (and typically) equipped. By the dry season of 1996-97, testing of the new local prototype took place in farmers' fields as well as on WARDA's research farms, with the IRRI engineer again assisting. Farmers participated in the equipment tests, indicating areas of concern with the design and operation. The advantage of using both local materials and local expertise was evident during the tests. Alternatives could be tested and minor changes made rapidly in the field or in the nearby artisan workshop, without major time delays. Thus, local artisans are in a good position to build, maintain, and repair the machines in the future.

In 1996, a second workshop was held to present test results from the latest thresher prototype and to discuss the commercial production of the thresher/cleaner. To reflect the integrated approach to product development, the name "ASI" was chosen, derived from ADRAO/SAED/ISRA, for the three agencies involved in Senegal (WARDA's French acronym is ADRAO). Then, in addition to the artisans, an agricultural machinery firm, SISMAR, was given the technical plans for the thresher/cleaner. Investing its own capital, SISMAR built a new

prototype, and assisted the WARDA/SAED/ISRA team in the tests and development of recommendations for the remaining modifications.

The ASI was officially released for commercial distribution on 5 November 1997. SISMAR has already manufactured machines for use in the Senegal River Valley and is unable to meet demand. Among the first purchasers of the ASI were two Senegalese farmers—local seed producers—who had participated in the tests and were impressed by the ASI performance rate, ease and safety of use, and quality of

output. Using the collaborative approach, this research and development effort was able to produce an adapted technology that addresses postharvest constraints with a domestically produced and easily repaired thresher/cleaner. Collaborative research by IRRI, ISRA, SAED, and WARDA was critical to ensuring a well-built, durable machine. The private sector, both artisans and the agroindustrial firm SISMAR, as well as farmers and their organizations, will determine the final diffusion of this machinery in Senegal. ■

Polyurethane rollers: a substitute for rubber rollers in rice dehuskers

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Thermoplastic polyurethane is formed by linking polyol and isocyanate. After a reaction, polyol becomes flexible and highly hydrophobic, and forms hydrolysis-stable polyurethanes. These two compounds, when mixed and undergoing reactions in different proportions and conditions, result in a polyurethane product of various hardness, tensile strength, elongation, and abrasion resistance. This polyurethane has applications in various industries such as automobiles, cold storage, footwear, etc. The major quality of polyurethane products is their abrasive resistance, which is approximately three times that of products made of rubber. In our study, polyurethane pieces were produced and tested to assess their suitability for replacing rubber rollers in rice dehuskers. The rubber rollers require frequent replacement because of the abrasive nature of the rice surface.

Polyol and isocyanate were mixed in different proportions (100:45, 100:50, 100:55, and 100:60) without any air bubbles forming in the mixture. This mix, poured in a mold for making test

Physical and mechanical properties of polyurethane specimens of various proportions of polyol and isocyanate and curing durations.

Curing duration (h)	Composition polyol:isocyanate	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation (%)	Hardness (°A)	Abrasion loss (cc 40 m ⁻¹)
2.5	100:45	6.19	158.50	82	0.35
	100:50	9.17	170.70	87	0.28
	100:55	10.00	182.90	88	0.24
	100:60	9.52	161.00	86	0.36
3.0	100:45	9.42	161.00	83	0.30
	100:50	11.20	178.05	89	0.24
	100:55	16.00	197.56	90	0.18
	100:60	12.43	170.70	87	0.32
3.5	100:45	8.00	143.90	83	0.30
	100:50	9.23	153.66	88	0.20
	100:55	13.38	173.70	89	0.13
	100:60	10.22	158.50	86	0.22
Commercial rubber roller		12.59	139.00	89	0.59

pieces, was cured at 90 ± 2 °C in an oven for 2.5, 3, and 3.5 h. These pieces were tested for hardness, tensile strength, elongation, and abrasion resistance using standard procedures (see table).

The table shows that all the properties required for use in the paddy dehusker-rubber roll type increased with a curing duration of 2.5 and 3 h and proportions of 100:45, 100:50, and 100:55, and decreased with 3.5 h of curing duration and proportion of

100:60. The tensile strength, elongation, and hardness of the test pieces were on a par with those of commercially available rubber rollers. The abrasion loss was in the range of 0.13–0.36 cc 40 m⁻¹ vs 0.59 cc 40 m⁻¹ for the rubber rollers. Tensile strength, elongation, and hardness were maximum at the proportion of 100:55 cured at 3 h with 0.18 cc 40 m⁻¹ of abrasion loss. This combination was thus identified as the optimum. ■

Manuscript preparation. Arrange the note as a brief statement of research objectives, a short description of project design, and a succinct discussion of results. Relate results to the objectives. Do not include abstracts. Do not cite references or include a bibliography. Restrain acknowledgments.